

THE ARTIST THAT OUR PEOPLE LOVE

KHursanoy TILLANAZAROVA

Republican music and art college teacher

Nature sometimes gives people such high generosity and talent that every listener who receives mental and spiritual nourishment from her art not only praises such a high talent, but also becomes a dedicated fan of artists. There are such musicians in the world of Uzbek art, whose services are worthy of praise in making our national songs more popular and popular among our people. He is one of our unique teachers, a great creative musician, a master composer, whose bright performance style, school, and national music heritage have been invaluable in imprinting our national musical heritage on the hearts of our people. One of our unique teachers, a great creative musician, skilled composer, who made an invaluable contribution to imprinting our national musical heritage in the hearts of our people with his brilliant performance style, school, People's Artist of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan, Medal "Fame", "Honor of the Country", "Fame of Labor", Abduhashim Ismailov is the recipient of the 'Order of Merit'. A creative party dedicated to the 70th anniversary of the birth of teacher Abduhoshim Ismailov was held at the Fergana Specialized Art School, a place that nurtures hundreds of talents, people's artists and people's hafiz, many winners of the "Nihal" and "Zulfiya" state awards. This historic day has become a real art festival for the teachers and students of the school. Abduhoshim Ismailov in his modern interpretation based on the heritage of traditional music of the Uzbek people is an artist who created his style and has a unique performance direction in the combination of these performances. Abduhashim Ismailov was born in 1952 in the village of Chaman, Kuva District, Fergana Region. He received his first lessons from his grandfather and mother, and from his uncle Omonjon and brother Sharofiddin Ismailov, who later became famous artists. The creative environment

that prevailed in Kuva district at that time also played an important role in his fate. Famous hafiz like Tavakkal Kadirov, Israeljon Usmanov could see young Abduhoshim's talent for art and recommended him to Fergana art school (now Fergana specialized art school). In the land of knowledge, he studies in the gijjak class of his teacher Omonjon Abdulkhakimov. Composer and musician Muhammadsiddiq Madaliev will learn traditional folk music performances. In 1975, he entered the Tashkent State Conservatory named after Mukhtar Ashrafiy to study "Oriental Music" enters the study and successfully completes it. Fakhridin Sadikov, Mahmudjon Muhammedov, He learns the ways of music and the secrets of composition from teachers such as Arif Alimakhsumov and Turgun Alimatov. Since 1975, his creative activity has been connected with the makomchilar ensemble named after Yunus Rajabi. At first, he worked in this ensemble as a musician, music director, later, until now, as an artistic director. Abduhoshim Ismailov's creative activity is reflected in several directions, the performance shows different aspects. First of all, if we take a look at his musical activity, as a skilled performer of the gijjak sozi, we will witness the creation of a performing school based on our classical musical heritage, continuing the traditions of master artists such as Komiljon Jabbarov, Ganijon Toshmatov, Gulomjon Khojikulov. On the other hand, based on the possibilities of the gijjak word, we see the performance styles in the modern interpretation as a means of performance skills. As an example of this, let's sing works composed by A. Ismailov such as "Holim Surma", "Dil Nolasi", "Kamon Nidosi", "Qalb Sadosi", "Toyona", "Gullola", "Hayoli Kiz", "Visol", "Uchrashuv" composed by A. Ismailov. possible We can see the further development of these performances in the form of works such as "Independence", "Fountain", "Big Maple", "I'm Surprised" performed by the "Uzbek Stars" ensemble with the participation of well-known musicians such as People's Artist of Uzbekistan Abdulahad Abdurashidov, Honored Artist of Uzbekistan Abdurahmon Holtojiev. The teacher's compositional creativity is also very rich, he composed songs of classical Uzbek poets "Dilinga ghamzadin",

"Yorsan", "Munavvar kil", "Ayriliq", "Yor emas", "Sarvinoz", "Tarahhum etmading", "Unutma", "Mushkuldir" ", "Yorima Ayting", "Angiz", "Janon karo kozingga", "Osmanda ham yo'q", "Uygonmasun" in thousands of works, the spirit of the ghazal and the harmony of the music achieve a wonderful performance. Based on the performance capabilities of popular singers beloved by our people, specially created songs are interpreted as a special edge of creativity. In cooperation with the Union of Composers and Composers of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek National Maqom Art Center, it was recommended to celebrate the jubilee dates of our master artists in 2022. Moreover, according to the plan of the Fergana specialized art school, since the beginning of the academic year, creative meetings and master classes have been organized by inviting a number of our people's favorite artists and experienced pedagogues. In this regard, in the Fergana specialized art school, the present day of our national music creative meeting and master class held with the participation of teacher Abduhoshim Ismailov made a great impression on students and teachers, as well as on all the guests who visited. At the event The participation of People's Artist of Uzbekistan Zulayho Boykhanova was a surprise for everyone. In addition, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Abdulahad Abdurashidov, Honored Artist of Uzbekistan Abdurahmon Holtojiev also participated.